

Cultural and creative sector representation for better policymaking

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Cultural and creative sector representation for better policymaking

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Introduction

The GPN approach challenges the traditional siloed (industry-based) conceptions of industries and domains and shows that boundaries and relationships between professions, firms, and industries in the CCS are much more fluid, dynamic, and permeable than is often assumed. By incorporating linkages, flows, and networks, the CICERONE methodology uncovers meaningful relationships between industries, sites, and local impacts, opening up new avenues for effective policymaking. Are these flows and relationships reflected in the way CCS stakeholders influence policymaking?

The section examines the policy ecosystem related to the CCS at the EU level by taking the policy network concept as a unit of analysis and determinant of policy outcomes. It aims to disentangle the organisational dynamics of the CCS networks at the EU level and examine the importance of interest groups' representation. A policy network means a set of relatively stable relationships which link various interdependent actors and share common interests about a policy area and exchange resources to pursue these shared interests, acknowledging that co-operation is the best way to achieve common goals (Borzel, 1998).

Policy networks are relevant because they comprise actors with varied spatial footprints given their multi-scalar membership. Most of these networks usually operate at the European level to influence EU policies and rules that impact CCS (such as on copyright, trade, competition, taxation, provision of services, and funding support). However, they are largely formed by a nation-based membership such as national associations or federations representing local specificities. The spatial footprint of interactions is therefore mostly European and national with some exceptions reflecting on the increased role played by local authorities in developing CCS.

This section focuses on the representation of interests at the EU policy level to assess the capacity of the sector to pursue the interests of the components of a global production network. The aim is to offer insights into how CCS function at their intermediation and representation at the policy level and whether current representation fits with a GPN approach. It proposes a taxonomy of CCS policy networks with an analysis of the impact of the current organisational setup on policymaking. Such analysis will include the insights from the stakeholders' roundtables carried out as part of the project. This will help distil general observations on CCS representation at EU level and the importance of CCS representation in addressing policymaking and policy gaps. Finally, the section proposes a set of recommendations to enable a better CCS representation in the capacity to deliver on policy objectives and CCS needs.

The issue is to practically assess the current degree of interaction of CCS with policymaking, its ability to represent the interests of CCS in policy development beyond sectoral regulatory issues. It also considers the capacity of policymakers to take decisions in line with a more complete understanding of the sector.

Through the GPN lenses policy strategies for CCS can be summarised as focused on supporting the creation and production phases at the local level through various support schemes (funding, regulation, etc.). Notably, there are no ‘CCS policies’ but policies for the various composite industries. This leads to confusion and unease from industry representatives (who naturally promote ‘sectoral’ (specific industry) interests. For misunderstanding CCS, policies often neglect the more comprehensive picture, notably in distribution and exchange, where much of the value is captured or lacks complementarity with a set of measures taken at local levels (city or regions).

Policy units at government and EU levels tend to cater to a limited number of CCS constituents to the exclusion of others: Each sector has its “guichet” which pursues different objectives. For instance, the film industry will interact mainly with DG CONNECT, design with DG GROW’s CCIS unit, and cultural organisations with its primary funder, DG EAC. Some sectors get to participate in developing industrial or environmental programs, but most are not even consulted. Sustainable development goals (SDGs) or artists’ social status are considered without the participation of industrial CCS networks (see the taxonomy of CCS policy networks below).

The fragmented engagement with CCS leads to the difficulty in comprehending holistically CCS’s contribution to innovation (development of new services and products), quality of life and health, international trade, or sustainability objectives. The CCS is embodied statistically but not as a sector on its own deserving a coherent policy framework catering to its specificities and common needs.

The CCS is worryingly absent from EU research programmes (Horizon Europe) or EU regional policies one of the most significant funding streams of EU actions¹ and who makes the development of SMEs and industrial competitiveness a key priority. The CCS is recognised as one of the EU’s 14 industrial ecosystems deserving a policy strategy. Still, little is done to integrate CCS in the consultation process that will serve to address policy priorities related to the Green Deal and the Digital agenda.

Based on the CICERONE findings, this section advocates the need to develop an EU cultural policy framework that will enable more coherent policy-making and a better representation of CCS interests across EU programmes.

¹ For the period 2021-2027 EU Horizon Europe that fund research and innovation has a budget of EUR 95 billion and the EU Cohesion Policy allocates EUR 392 billion.

CCS representation matters. This can be illustrated in relation to two recent major EU policy initiatives: establishing a Knowledge Innovation Community (KIC) for culture and creativity and implementing the Resilience and Recovery Facility (RRF).

Both policy initiatives are cross-sectoral and trans-disciplinary in their objectives. They both relate to the CCS as an agent of economic wealth and social transformation on the one hand and as a sector requiring priority treatment following the impact of the COVID-19 pandemic on the other. The response of the CCS to these essential policy initiatives with considerable financial support demonstrates the need to revisit CCS representation and its organisation.

KIC stands for Knowledge Innovation Community². In October 2019 a new KIC focused on the culture and creative sector to financially support a KIC for CCS over a 7-year period (renewable once) was announced. The winning consortium was selected in the course of 2022. Examining the partners willing to participate in this project is an exciting lesson on mobilising CCS beyond sectoral policies.

EIT Culture & Creativity brings together 50 partners from across Europe to manage the program. The winning consortium has tried its best to recruit the industrial component of the consortium (to work with academics and research centres). Despite these efforts, out of 50 partners only four will represent the business side of the CCS in Europe (Philips Design, Ogilvy, Mediapro and the EBU). It is true that smaller enterprises or entrepreneurs will find representation through local clusters and hubs. The great majority of consortium members leading the project are from the non-industrial side of the CCS representation spectrum. Can and should the EIT investment priorities be developed without their participation?

The consideration might not be so important considering:

- the importance and value of State and public intervention in shaping production networks at EU level.
- The attempt to build cross-sectorial representation in the EIT management.
- The capacity of public institutions to consider long-term, strategic policy objectives.

² KICs are managed by the European Institute of Technology and Innovation (EIT), an EU body, reporting to the European Commission (DG Education, Research and Culture). With a EUR 2.9 billion budget (2021-2027) it aims to support innovation in the EU. The main instrument is the implementation of KICs focused on industry specifics and societal issues. There have been since 2009 the EIT has supported 8 KICs (on Health, Mobility, Energy, Raw Materials, Digital, Manufacturing etc.). A KIC to do what? Essentially to help CCS confront various challenges and investment needs. This includes:

- To cluster creative skills and competences.
- To incubate innovative start-ups and scale up.
- To test and prototype new services and products.
- To fund and invest in new ventures.
- To pool resources (human and financial) to help the sector grow and contribute to economic and social innovation within the CCS but also in other sectors (environment, mobility, social cohesion, circular economy, health, quality of life etc.).
- To support collaboration with the technology sector.

Areas of research would include important competitiveness topics such as data management, user interface, standards, revenue models, rights licensing, and management, blockchain, artificial intelligence (AI), etc.

However, it becomes essential if one believes it is more challenging to address competitiveness issues without the production network and its representatives³.

Another example relates to the adoption by the European Union of a Recovery and Resilience Facility (RRF) to help Member States weather the COVID pandemic crisis and its consequences. The Facility is a temporary recovery instrument. It allows the Commission to raise funds to help Member States implement reforms and investments that align with the EU's priorities. It makes available €723.8 billion in loans (€385.8 billion) and grants (€338 billion) for that purpose. The RRF is aimed to help the EU achieve its target of climate neutrality by 2050 and sets Europe on a path of digital transition, creating jobs and spurring growth in the process.

The European Commission was decisive in indicating that CCS is a priority sector to benefit from the RRF, considering the harmful impact of the pandemic on the sector. The path to the digital transition added to the importance given to CCS as a primary beneficiary of the fund. Despite a favourable political environment, the RRF represents a missed opportunity to work jointly across CCS networks and sectors to influence policy-making at EU and national levels and make the most of post-covid recovery resources to address policy gaps. CCS representation failed to develop a coherent and cohesive action plan to influence Member States' strategies. At the end, it found satisfaction in reaching an overall threshold of 2% of the funding going to the CCS, used mainly for safeguarding cultural heritage.

To conclude with another example on CCS representation lies with an event organized on 28 February 2023, Culture Action Europe (CAE), European Cultural Foundation (ECF) and Europa Nostra, the largest non-industrial CCS networks to promote culture as essential in shaping the EU policy agenda and in strengthening the CCS ecosystem as part of the campaign 'Cultural Deal for Europe'⁴. The industrial side of the CCS is not involved in this important political initiative, thus weakening its impact. It would be like organizing a forum on health policy without the participation of private hospitals, doctors, trade unions, and the pharmaceutical industry. Does this serve the objective of mainstreaming culture in broader policy objectives?

It is commonly agreed that CCS in the EU represents a sector of the economy valued at €477 billion (close to 4% of EU value added) with around 8 million jobs and 1.2 million enterprises, essentially SMEs. But who speaks for the CCS, one of the EU's largest and most dynamic sectors? How does CCS participate in policymaking?

³ When EU industrial policy networks are asked why they are not involved in a policy initiative to support their development, they explain that they lack the financial and human resources to contribute to such a large-scale and complex program.

⁴ <https://cultureactioneurope.org/news/a-cultural-deal-for-europe/>

1. Cultural and creative sector representation at EU level

The research identified more than 100 CCS networks active in influencing policies at the EU level.⁵ This section is proposing a taxonomy of the various CCS policy networks in the EU. It features a representation of the quantitative importance of the types of networks and sectorial representation based on the proposed taxonomy.

Table 1. Types of CCS policy networks

EU CCS POLICY NETWORKS	Industrial networks			Non-industrial networks		
	Trade Associations	CMO	Trade Unions	NGOs	Public institutions	Local and regional authorities
Policy focus	Competition/ jobs Resilience and diversity	Working conditions Resilience/ diversity	Working conditions Resilience/ diversity	Working conditions SDGs Resilience and diversity	Competitiveness and jobs Resilience/ diversity	Territorial development Resilience/ diversity
Main EC partner	DG CNECT, DG GROW, DG EAC	DG CNECT, DG EAC	DG CNECT, DG EMPL	DG EAC, DG RTD	DG CNECT, DG EAC, DG INTPA DG RTD	DG EAC, DG REGIO
Spatial Interaction	European National	European National	European National	European National Local	European National	European Local
Phases (Focus)	Production Distribution Exchange	Creation Production Archive	Creation Production	Creation	Creation Production Distribution Archive Exchange	Creation Production Exchange
Source of Funding	Majority self-funded	Majority self-funded	Majority self-funded	Significant EU-funding	Majority self-funded	Significant EU-funding

⁵ List of CCS policy networks are found in the Annex 1

Key characteristics of policy networks

There is a great variety of CCS policy networks. The table summarising the types of CCS policy networks (see Table 1, previous page) aims to characterise their respective activities. We distinguish these activities along:

- **Policy aims** – the focus of policy activities with public authorities.
- **Spatial interactions** – the level of governance mainly targeted for policy purposes (local, national, European).
- **Main EC partners** – focus of interactions with European Commission’s services.
- **Phases of the GPN** – the phases of PN mostly represented (among creation, production, distribution, exchange, archive).
- **Source of funding** – to distinguish between networks that are mostly self-funded from those that are significantly relying on EU funding.

Figure 1. Distribution of CCS policy networks by type (as a % of 112 networks)

2. Analysis of EU cultural and creative sector networks and general observations

This section will examine the types of CCS networks, propose general observations on CCS representation in light of the GPN approach and consider impact of such representation on EU policies. There are two main types of EU CCS Networks – industrial and non-industrial networks. At the end of this section, we will consider a third type of CCS network: the mixed CCS networks.

EU industrial CCS networks

EU industrial networks comprise:

1. **Trade organisations** representing sectoral interests in the various industrial subsectors of the CCS (music, film, games, book publishing, broadcasting) – such as DOT Europe, IFPI, IMPALA, EBU, ACT, FEP, ISFE, CEIPI, UNIC, EBU, Europeanvodcoalition, Eurovod, ACE⁶ etc.
2. **Collective rights management organisations** (CMO) representing the interests of rights holders in the various subsectors where collective rights management structures operate (music authors/composers, music publishers, performers and musicians), film (performers, authors), visual arts such as GESAC, AEPO/ARTIS, SAA, EVA, etc.
3. **Trade Unions** and organisations representing the interests of authors, artists, actors, musicians such as FIM/FIA/ ECSA /FERA, etc.

Industrial policy networks have as a main mandate to safeguard the economic interests of their members in the face of EU extensive regulatory powers that impact the functioning and development of culture and creative industries in the field of copyright, taxation (VAT), audio-visual media services, protection of minors, digital competition, or trade law.

The main interlocutors at EU institutional levels are the European Commission Directorate Generals in charge of internal market, competition, and trade rules. At the European Parliament we find the committees dealing with legal affairs and industrial policy. However, at Council level the sector must interact mainly with representatives of Member States in charge of cultural policy.

⁶ Acronyms of organisations are explained in Annex 4.

The three main Directorate Generals at the European Commission in charge of managing specific EU funded programs with an industrial CCS objective are:

- The Directorate-General for Communications Networks, Content and Technology (DG CONNECT) which manages the MEDIA strand of the Creative Europe program (€ 226.5 million in 2022 out of € 385.6 million) in its audio-visual dimension (essentially support to the cinema sector and the pan-European distribution of films)⁷. DG Connect is also running schemes aimed at encouraging investment of financial institutions in CCS via the Guarantee Facility for CCS⁸ or Invest EU⁹.
- The Directorate General Education, Youth, Sport (DGEAC) in so far as its Creative Europe program supports industries (through awards in publishing or architecture, translation and dubbing, development of a music industry support scheme, support to a network of concert halls). DGEAC managed € 166 million in 2022.
- The Directorate General for Internal Market, Industry, Entrepreneurship and SMEs (DG GROW), which manages policies and support mechanisms for enterprises. DG GROW is responsible for implementing an EU industry strategy that seeks to mobilise ecosystems to accelerate the green and digital transition through various support mechanisms (Invest EU, Euroclusters, Erasmus Young Entrepreneurs....) and various governance tools (Single Market Report, Confidence Indicators, Industrial Forum). A policy unit at DG GROW is committed to reinforcing CCS's engagement to make the CCS industrial ecosystem more resilient and competitive.

Industrial policy networks play an important role to shape the regulatory environment of the cultural sector, the promotion of cultural diversity principles that will often justify different treatment from market rules applying to other industries to take into account the cultural dimension of their activities (for instance rules on copyright, geo-blocking, state aid, VAT rates, digital services, etc.).

Industrial policy networks' scope of activities includes:

- Collecting statistical information on sales and market development.
- Developing voluntary codes and EU-wide standards.
- Monitoring and carrying out lobby activities to influence the regulatory environment and policymaking.
- Mobilise, negotiate, and exchange resources within their membership.
- Coordination with their members at the national level to ensure consistency in implementing EU rules to align with the organisation's position.

⁷ European Commission, Directorate-General for Education, Youth, Sport and Culture, (2021). Creative Europe 2021-2027: the EU program supporting the cultural and creative sectors, Publications Office of the European Union.

⁸ https://www.eif.org/what_we_do/guarantees/cultural_creative_sectors_guarantee_facility/index.htm;
https://ec.europa.eu/commission/presscorner/detail/it/MEMO_16_2346

⁹ https://investeu.europa.eu/index_en

The various networks operate separately with their staff and premises. To a large extent, they depend on the goodwill and intrinsic motivation of a staff committed to the cultural cause. Most of the organisations are based in Brussels. They are registered at the EU Transparency Register¹⁰, a public database established in 2021 for interest groups to declare activities and relations with EU institutions. These organisations sometimes form ad-hoc coalitions pooling their lobby resources to defend a common and particular interest vis-à-vis a more powerful lobby group or a given policy process. Such informal collaborations start with a manifesto or a call to action and can later develop into a more formal organisation. For instance, Creativity Works! is a coalition gathering federations of authors, producers, and distributors right holders from various sectors to contribute a single voice on the impact of digital distribution on the European copyright ecosystem focusing on broadcasting, geo-blocking, and copyright regulation. Such a constellation of actors on a cross-sectorial level is organically driven. It follows a logic of case-based emergency tied to the necessity of pooling resources to defend a joint interest in the face of larger and more powerful lobby groups representing the tech industry, notably the GAFAN.¹¹

Trade organisations are funded by their membership, often a mix of national trade associations and corporate members. CMOs represent national collecting societies and the respective individual members (authors, performers, or producers) that entrusted these societies to collect copyright royalties.

Trade Unions and professional associations representing individual creators remain poorly funded at the EU level.

Industrial networks do not rely on EU funding for their activities unless they participate in some EU-funded project to promote the circulation of European works and artists. Multinational and large CCS companies are members of trade associations. Often, in addition, they have their own representation office or department in charge of public affairs (for instance, Bertelsmann, Canal Plus, Universal, ARD, etc.). Their spatial interaction is both at the European and national levels as the policy networks will seek to influence a proper implementation of EU rules at the national level. They have limited relations with local and regional authorities while the latter are increasingly active in supporting the development of culture and creative industries (see section 1).

EU non-industrial CCS networks

Three types of networks represent the non-industrial CCS networks:

¹⁰ <https://ec.europa.eu/transparencyregister/public/homePage.do?locale=en#en>

¹¹ The organisation Digital Europe (digitaleurope.org) has among its members companies such as Amazon, Apple, Meta, Google. The Motion Picture Association (mpa-emea.org) represents the global film, television and streaming industry (Disney, Netflix, Paramount, Sony Pictures, Universal, Warner Bros).

1. **Non-governmental organisations** (NGOs) gathering essentially not-for-profit cultural and social organisations (CAE, IETM, Europa Nostra, Trans-Europe Hall, etc.).
2. **National public agencies** gathering governmental agencies in charge of managing aspects of the national cultural policy (national film agencies (EFAD), national culture promotion centres (EUNIC), etc.).
3. **Local authorities** representing cities and regions looking at culture as part of local development activities (ERRIN, Eurocities, ENCC, a part of ECBN membership).

The main mandate of these networks is to promote public interest objectives. The scope of activities includes:

- Influencing the EU cultural agenda and work plan.
- Fostering networking opportunities within their membership.
- Offering training and development opportunities.
- Demanding more EU consideration and funding to culture.
- Contributing to audience development and providing visibility to Europe's values and different cultures.
- Promoting the mobility of cultural workers and artists.
- Highlighting the importance of culture in the European project or the UN SDGs.

These networks are generally more dependent on EU funding, which has often been instrumental to their creation or key to funding their activities. Local authorities (regions, municipalities) increasingly use structural and cohesion funds to develop smart local CCS ecosystems. They are actively contributing to European cultural initiatives coordinating actions, and sharing experiences, notably in the field of cultural heritage. The networks are instrumental in sharing good local cultural asset management practices for economic and social development.

Mixed CCS networks

These are a few EU networks combining to some extent industrial and non-industrial interests and/or that are cross-sectorial at the industry level. Cross-sectorial collaboration is in its infancy, however encouraged by policymakers. Cross-sectorial representation is more prevalent in non-industrial networks (Cultural NGOs with a network such CAE).

This mixed category has been gaining relevance at the EU level. This is evident when looking at the latest Creative Europe Program 2021-2027 where one of the three main strands is supporting cross-sectorial collaboration "aimed at reinforcing collaboration between different cultural and creative sectors, to help them address the common challenges they face and find innovative new solutions »¹².

¹² <https://culture.ec.europa.eu/creative-europe/cross-sectorial-strand>

Pioneering this trend of trans-disciplinary and cross-sectorial collaboration, we should highlight three existing networks:

- The European Creative Business Network (ECBN)¹³ was founded in 2011 to promote the interests of the cultural creative industries in Europe. ECBN membership includes agencies, funders, and public intermediaries at local, regional, and/or national levels that support their cultural and creative entrepreneurs.
- bcreative, in Brussels, stems from an initiative of the European Parliament in 2016 to support establishing an international platform to network cultural and creative entrepreneurs across the world and across disciplines¹⁴. The membership is a mix of individuals, companies, and agencies.
- The Creative Business Network¹⁵ is a European-based initiative to network creative start-ups and investors. It essentially organises a competition: the Creative Business Cup. The foundation established in Denmark also participates in several EU-funded projects.

Co-Funded by Creative Europe, Creative Flip¹⁶ is a preparatory action (to run until the end of 2023) aimed at strengthening the “cultural and creative sectors and industries” overall ecosystem through cross-sectorial collaboration and activities. The activities include the setting up of a platform “Creatives Unite” for CCS to share information and good practices. The platform is operated by the Goethe-Institut and the European Creative Hubs network¹⁷ a non-profit association representing “more than 300 creative hubs in Europe”. However, the level of participation of the industrial CCS networks in this initiative is not clear.

In the same spirit the European Institute of Technology (EIT) is since 2022 funding a network ‘culture and creativity’ to support innovation in the CCS. The consortium managing the Knowledge Innovation Community (KIC) comprises a mixed membership gathering universities, research centres, local creative hubs, cities, CCS networks, and corporations.¹⁸

Substantial EU-wide cross-sectorial collaboration and networks amongst CCS and other industries notably in the digital sector is yet to be achieved. The EIT KIC initiative is an attempt to address this representation gap.

¹³ <https://www.ecbnetwork.eu/what-we-do/>

¹⁴ <https://bcreativetracks.com> – the network became an association in 2019. The secretariat is managed by KEA, main author of this document.

¹⁵ <https://www.cbnet.com/network>

¹⁶ <https://creativeflip.creativehubs.net/project-2/>

¹⁷ <http://creativehubs.net/>

¹⁸ <https://eit.europa.eu/eit-community/eit-culture-creativity>

Cross-sectorial collaboration involving industrial actors is increasingly taking place in some European countries:

- Established in 2021, Creative UK¹⁹ is an independent network. It unites all parts of the UK's culture and creative sector "with one voice, holding government to account and campaigning for change". It has set three policy priorities for 2022-23: Redesigning Freelancing, Accessing Finance and Championing Creative Skills. Its aim is uniting the CCS in the UK and generating innovation to shape the UK's cultural, social, and economic context. To do this they provide services to both young creatives and established businesses and individuals through two forms of membership for students and federations. The first one is aimed at helping young creatives to start building their path in the sector through networking events, workshops, and tools for professional development. The second one, provides services such as networking, access to funding and programs. Its advocacy covers topics of "People, Place, and Planet".
- In the Netherlands on 20 Mai 2021, the Dutch Design Foundation, Federatie Creatieve Industrie, CLICKNL and the Centre of Expertise for Creative Innovation announced joining forces in 'The Open Coalition'. The goal "is to combine knowledge, skills and experience around how the Dutch cultural and creative industries can play a bigger role in solving societal challenges"²⁰.
- In Austria as part of the Austrian Federal Economic Chamber, Kreativwirtschaft Austria²¹ represents the interests of the cultural creative industries and advocate for the visibility of creative industry-based services. Kreativwirtschaft Austria (KAT) offers comprehensive services for the economic success of creative professionals and their cross-industry networking.
- In Estonia, since 2009 Creative Estonia²² is a CCI Cluster and development centre, which promotes and develops creative industries and creative businesses in Estonia.

Policy recommendations below stress the importance of building Creative Europe as a network uniting the various CCS policy networks to enable better engagement with cross-sectorial policy initiatives on skills, digital transformation or that enable the scaling up of CCS ecosystems.

¹⁹ Creative UK <https://www.wearecreative.uk/>

²⁰ <http://dutchcreativeindustries.nl/2021/05/20/dutch-cultural-and-creative-industries-join-forces-in-the-open-coalition/>

²¹ <https://www.kreativwirtschaft.at/en/>

²² <https://www.looveesti.ee/en/creative-estonia/>

2.1 Examples of CCS policy networks typology at the EU level

The CCS Policy Networks typology is a framework developed through a series of observations and mapping exercises. The goal of this taxonomy is to provide an effective tool for analysing and categorizing CCS representation ecosystems, in order to better understand the practical policy reality. In this context, we present a series of real-life examples of CCS representation organizations, aimed at illustrating each type of policy network. However, it is important to note that the main types of CCS policy networks still contain a great deal of heterogeneity in terms of size, shape, and scope. Therefore, while these examples are solid representations within the ecosystem, they should not be taken as definitive cases for each type. The following table provides a list of six examples of CCS policy networks, alongside a description of their primary goals and policy activities.

The CCS Policy Networks typology is a framework developed through a series of observations and mapping exercises. The goal of this taxonomy is to provide an effective tool for analysing and categorizing CCS representation ecosystems, in order to better understand the practical policy reality. In this context, we present a series of real-life examples of CCS representation organizations, aimed at illustrating each type of policy network. However, it is important to note that the main types of CCS policy networks still contain a great deal of heterogeneity in terms of size, shape, and scope. Therefore, while these examples are solid representations within the ecosystem, they should not be taken as definitive cases for each type. The following table provides a list of six examples of CCS policy networks, alongside a description of their primary goals and policy activities.

Table 2. CCS policy network examples

CCS policy network type	Example	Description
Trade Organisation	Federation of European Publishers (FEP)	The Federation of European Publishers represents 29 national associations of publishers of books, learned journals and educational materials of the European Union, the European Economic Area and other European countries.
CMO	European Grouping of Societies of Authors and Composers (GESAC)	GESAC brings together 32 rights management bodies in Europe, collecting royalties on behalf of authors in the field of music and audiovisual and music publishers. It acts in the name of its members (1 million authors) in the discussions and negotiations with the European Institutions.

Trade Unions	International Federation of Actors (FIA)	The International Federation of Actors is a global union federation bringing together trade unions representing actors. It represents several hundreds of thousands of performers with some 90 member organisations in more than 60 countries around the world.
Public Agencies	European Film Agencies (EFAD)	The European Film Agency Directors brings together 37 film and audiovisual national agencies in charge of funding, advising, and regulating mainly the film sector in Europe.
NGOs	International network for contemporary performing arts (IETM)	IETM represents the voice of over 500 member organisations and individual professionals working in the contemporary performing arts worldwide.
Local Authorities	Eurocities	Eurocities is a network of large cities in Europe including over 200 of Europe's major cities from 38 countries. Although is not a culture specific organization, it works on managing large European projects in the field of culture notably in cultural heritage.

2.2 General observations on cultural and creative sector representation at EU-level

The mapping of CCS representation shows a wide variety of organisations working at different governance levels of policymaking, with different interlocutors and concerning various interests in the different phases of production networks.

The representation is siloed between industrial and non-industrial interests, on the one hand, as well as between the different stakeholders in the value chain, on the other: artists, creators, performers, producers, and distributors. It is essential to highlight that CCS policy networks share several important policy objectives.

Table 3. CCS networks' common policy objectives

Raise policy awareness	Ensure policymakers recognise and implement policies that acknowledge the economic, social, and cultural significance of the Cultural and Creative Sector (CCS). The goods and services provided by CCS, such as music, film, literature, and visual arts, not only have the potential to create wealth but also contribute to social inclusion, education, health, individual self-confidence, and our collective way of life.
Mainstream culture into public interest	Emphasise that culture is not just about generating wealth but also about promoting values such as freedom of expression and advancing public interest objectives. The European Union has set a precedent by establishing cultural diversity as an international law principle and demonstrating that cultural products deserve specific treatment, not just as mere commodities.
Broaden the value of culture	Acknowledge the importance of capturing social, educational, and creative value in addition to the value derived from the exploitation of distribution networks and copyright assets. Policy efforts should prioritise value capture that considers the social and educational impact of cultural products and creation.
Encourage public support	Highlight the need for public support, whether through funding or regulation, to encourage investment in the CCS, generate new creations, and audiences. Public support can include art education at schools to foster a deeper appreciation for cultural and creative endeavours.

Nevertheless, the capacity of CCS networks to influence policymaking whether at EU and national levels is constrained by the following factors:

1. Lack of engagement between industrial and non-industrial policy networks

The difficulty of the non-industrial policy network to engage with the industrial policy networks on the ground is that the latter's intrinsic motivation would be purely and solely commercial. On this basis, non-industrial policy networks underestimate the importance of intellectual property rights, international trade, or competition law as instruments to promote cultural diversity or investment in art and culture. They rarely join forces with the industrial policy networks to push for regulations aimed at reinforcing industrial capacity and addressing competitiveness issues. They often lack the resources to follow technical debates requiring legal and institutional expertise. The persisting confrontation between industrial and non-industrial CCS actors contributes to perpetuating a lack of consensus at policy level on the meaning of culture and its impacts. This failure curtails the capacity to influence policymaking beyond sectoral interests and develop a more comprehensive narrative on cultural investment's societal, economic, and sustainability impact.

2. Lack of resources of industrial policy networks

The industrial policy networks are not sufficiently resourced to consider wider policy objectives (beyond their narrow sectoral interests) linked to competitiveness, sustainability development or social regeneration goals for instance. As a result, they do not participate in large EU funding programmes aimed at supporting industry competitiveness such as Horizon Europe on research an innovation or Cohesion policy (for regional development). "CCIS are not supported enough" admitted recently a commission official working in Horizon Europe. Despite opportunities and supportive policy intentions, industrial policy networks do not seem to be equipped to make the most of EU policies and programmes. As a result, the role of cultural and creative entrepreneurs in addressing broader policy challenges, in triggering innovation and creating valuable intangible assets or in supporting international partnerships (external relations) are not sufficiently tackled from an industrial point of view. The industry side also fails to rally the cultural lobby to assert the importance of cultural rights or to consider the importance of their activities in accompanying social transformation, promoting human rights and democracy, intercultural dialogue or in contributing to building a cultural narrative on the European project. These policy objectives are left to the non-industrial networks led by either public bodies or non-governmental actors.²³

Key actors missing in CCS representation

CCS representation is missing some important actors:

²³ A good example of this was the "New Narrative for Europe" project in 2014, when EC President Barroso commissioned to a group artists, intellectuals, politicians, and head of public institutions to connect the general public with the European integration project via the arts and culture. Publishers, producers, editors, distributors and a large portion of cultural practitioners are insufficiently mobilised in the process of crafting a new vision for Europe at a time of great political, technological and environmental challenges.

- Powerful CCS companies notably in the fashion and design sector (the large international brands from the so-called “high-end industries” – such as Gucci, Hermès or LVMH) are reluctant to be considered as part of CCS with the consequences that they would be marginalised in the “cultural ghetto” of policy making.
- Large European digital streaming services and e-commerce platforms trading CCS goods and services are insufficiently contributing to the policy debate, thus preventing a good understanding of digital transformations and money flows in production phases.
- The local dimension of CCS deserves better consideration as creation and production are intrinsically linked to a territory. Local authorities (notably cities) have become essential partners in developing cultural and creative ecosystems, often associating cultural enterprises with tech. and social enterprises. A spatial mismatch between the most critical phases of value creation in the CCS GPN and the representation efforts vis-à-vis policymakers should not be allowed to develop. As mentioned above, the cohesion policy whose mission is to support SMEs and regional economic development is hardly subject to influence from CCS policy networks.

As a result, the siloed, incomplete, and spatially fragmented approach undermines the capacity of CCS to influence the policy agenda or benefit from EU programmes (increasingly open to CCS) and for policy-makers to apprehend the entire CCS ecosystem or engage with it. This largely contributes to preventing the building of a coherent EU policy for the whole CCS.

The capacity of CCS to influence the policy agenda and for policy-makers to address policy gaps can be illustrated as follows:

1. Adversary forces can play one against the other to undermine the overall CCS interests. Cultural activists may rally tech companies in battles on the exercise of intellectual property rights for instance. Support to CCS through market mechanisms (such as the Guarantee Facility for the CCS)²⁴ is perceived as undermining public subsidies for the non-for-profit sector, and little effort is made to use the facility.
2. Policy documents from cultural ministries remain largely focused on addressing issues from a public sector’s perspective.²⁵
3. International partnerships and relations are often developed whilst focusing on people-to-people dialogue ignoring the trade or business dimension in intercultural exchanges whilst international distribution of cultural goods is a powerful means to share values and “seduce” hearts and minds. A book, a performance or a sound recording may not save the world, but they may change lives, open up new horizons and contribute to individual emancipation. Cultural goods and performances create spaces for freedom and imagination. CCS representatives should occupy a

²⁴ EU Guarantee Facility for the Cultural and Creative Sector – a €121 Million financial instrument set up in 2016 and managed by the European Investment Fund (EIF) to encourage bank loans in CCS.

²⁵ For instance, latest Council paper on the environment (January 2023) considering support to the green transition is limited to cultural public institutions (museum, performing arts) neglecting the contribution of the industrial section of CCS. Likewise, the Council Resolution on the EU workplan for Culture 2023-2026, while delineating ambitious priority areas for EU cultural policy fails short on suggesting actions to support the industrial competitiveness and growth of the CCS.

larger role in the EU trade and international partnerships as a key sector of the European economies and of EU soft power.

4. The European Parliament (EP) has recently taken the initiative to consider EU action to improve the social status of artists and cultural workers. In the next few months, the EP is expected to work on an 'own initiative report' for the "Framework for a European Status of the Artists". The EP Committee on Culture and Education (CULT) is acting on the basis of Article 225 of the Treaty on the Functioning of the EU, i.e., allows the Parliament to request the Commission to submit "appropriate proposals on matters on which it considers that a Union act is required to implement the Treaties." The European Commission takes the view that the EU has no or limited competence in the matter. It remains to be seen at which level of representations CCS will contribute to this critical political issue, notably the involvement of trade unions representing cultural workers and the trade associations representing employers and producers. This should be an opportunity for cross-sectorial work.
5. Among the CCS some sectors have representation problems of their own, notably in fashion and design:

Fashion

There are numerous European associations deemed to represent the sector: The European Fashion Council (EFC)²⁶, the European Fashion Heritage Association (EFHA)²⁷, and the European Fashion Alliance (EFA)²⁸. However, their representativity is questioned as the important European fashion brands (LVMH, Kering, Richemont, Boss etc) are represented through their national associations (Altagamma, Comité Colbert....) in a separate organisation: the European Cultural and Creative Industries Alliance (ECCIA)²⁹ specialised in representing "High-End products". European fashion brands which exercise worldwide domination in the sector contribute hardly to overall cultural and CCS policy, focusing their resources on limited sectoral industrial priorities (fight against counterfeiting, promote image as a competitive European industry). The manufacturing side of the industry seems to be better organised and involved with Euratex. The trade organisation represents the textile & clothing national associations and European branch associations. Euratex is a member of the consortium managing the EIT KIC culture and creativity initiative for instance. Is Euratex representative of the CCS in all its production phases?

Design

The design industry is one of the largest sectors of CCS in term of employment (around 800,000 designers in the EU according to Bureau of European Designers Associations (BEDA)) and value-added as well as in its capacity to bring innovation to other industries and day-to-day life. At the EU level, the main representative body for Designers is BEDA³⁰. BEDA boasts 54 members from 28 countries in Europe. Members are essentially design promotion centres and other publicly

²⁶ <https://europaregina.eu/organizations/trade-associations/fashion/europe/european-fashion-council/>

²⁷ <https://fashionheritage.eu>

²⁸ <https://www.europeanfashionalliance.org>

²⁹ <https://www.eccia.eu>

³⁰ <https://www.beda.org>

funded organizations that promote design nationally or regionally. With the co-funding of the Creative Europe Program, BEDA's main aim is to enhance the awareness and understanding of the value of design. Designers, as individuals or corporations are not directly influencing the agenda of BEDA. Is limiting the sectors' representation to public institutions constraining policy-making capacity to support the deployment of creative industries?

Finally, CCS representation is preventing the building of a coherent EU policy for CCS notably at the level of the European Commission which initiates policy actions:

1. The Directorate General Education, Youth, Sport (DGEAC) generally tends to valorise culture in its societal dimension as a way to promote EU values, citizenship, intercultural dialogue, better health and artists' mobility more in the realm of EU subsidiary competence. It provides essential support through Creative Europe to networks of cultural workers throughout the EU and platforms enabling cultural workers (such as Culture Action Europe, Europa Nostra or IETM) to develop pan European projects and speak out for culture as an essential element of the European project. It has taken important initiatives to support a more cross-sectoral collaboration by funding projects such as Creative Flip. It remains that industrial networks have yet to be active in these networks. DG EAC is attempting, with limited resources, to support some structural projects in the music and book publishing sectors such as promoting a sustainable European music ecosystem (Music Moves Europe – MME)³¹ or connecting emerging literary artists through talent development (CELA)³².
2. The Directorate-General for Communications Networks, Content and Technology (DG CONNECT) notably in the management of the MEDIA strand of Creative Europe focuses its attention on the needs of the audio-visual sector, thus leaving aside important and competitive cultural assets in other copyright industries such as music or publishing. DG Connect is leading on critical regulatory developments linked to copyright, the regulation of media and the provision of AV and digital services. This DG has less contact with the non-industrial side of CCS policy networks.
3. The Directorate General for Internal Market, Industry, Entrepreneurship and SMEs (DG GROW) manages the implementation of the Single Market Program (4.2 billion EUR from 2021 to 2027), which aims to strengthen the governance of the Single Market. Its role is to help improve the internal market, including boosting the competitiveness of businesses, particularly SMEs. The DG's work is organised around 14 industrial ecosystems, the new paradigm integrating policy perspective across goods and services and the coordination hubs for cross-cutting issues within the DG such as “green”, “digitalization” or “standards”. DG Grow has yet to focus on “culture and creative industries” the terminology used by this DG, identified as one of the 14 industrial ecosystems. On 4 April 2022 the Council adopted conclusions on “building a European strategy for the cultural and creative industries (CCIE) ecosystem.” We will address below the different

³¹ Music Moves Europe (MME) is the result of a policy process started in 2015 to find ways to support and promote the European music sector. It has become a framework for all the European Commission's initiatives and actions in support of the European music sector with more than 130 music projects during the programming period 2014-2020.

³² CELA trains and connects 30 emerging authors, 80 emerging translators and 6 emerging literary professionals offering a bigger opportunity to less used languages.

policy objectives of DG Grow mainly working with some CCS sectors such as the design, large media publishers and high-end industries.

4. The Directorate General for International Partnerships (DG INTPA) and Directorate-General for Neighbourhood and Enlargement Negotiations (DG NEAR) responsible for international relations and neighbourhood policies respectively rarely engage with the culture and creative industries despite increased demand from third countries for support to help develop a local sustainable CCS industry as an instrument of growth and jobs. EUNIC – the European Union National Institutes for Culture – is the European network of national public cultural organizations engaging in cultural relations. It is one of the European networks supported by the Creative Europe program of the European Union and this since 2014. Since 2019 EUNIC has partnered with the European Commission and the European External Action Service (EEAS) to work on the cultural dimension of international relations³³. It would seem relevant to also build international partnerships to help third countries manage their local industry’s copyright and build local cultural and creative ecosystems that contribute to economic and social development³⁴.
5. Horizon Europe, the EU research program in its social science and humanities dimension and structural funds part of EU cohesion policy (€ 392 billion for the period 2021-2027) aimed at regions also contribute to providing support to CCS. Horizon Europe also funds the programme S+T+ARTS³⁵, to support collaboration between artists, scientists and engineers. No evaluation has taken place yet on the contribution of the EU research programme (€95 billion) to the development of CCS. So far Horizon Europe funding has mostly benefitted research in tangible cultural heritage with the prospect of establishing a European Partnership³⁶ to fund research in the area³⁷. The EIT KIC on culture and creativity is a critical step to engage with CCS, provided the latter are in a capacity to influence its research agenda.
6. DG REGIO is in charge of implementing the Cohesion Policy, a very large part of EU’s budget devoted to correcting imbalances between countries and regions. Many regions have developed policies to support the development of CCS notably through Smart Specialisation as part of industrial strategy. To what extent CCS policy networks at the EU level can influence and contribute to the definition and implementation of EU Cohesion Policy?
7. It is essential to mention The New European Bauhaus a creative and interdisciplinary initiative from the President of the European Commission aimed “at connecting the European Green Deal to our living spaces and experiences”. The New European Bauhaus “calls on all of us to imagine and build together a sustainable and inclusive future that is beautiful for our eyes, minds, and souls”³⁸. This policy initiative is a desire expressed at the highest EU political level to mobilise

³³ <https://eunic.eu/joint-guidelines> Joint guidelines: EC – EEAS-EUNIC partnership

³⁴ See for instance Morocco/EU partnership programme to support the development of culture and creative industries (2023-2027).

³⁵ <https://starts.eu/>

³⁶ The aim of European Partnerships with EU and associated countries, the private sector, foundations and other stakeholders is to deliver on global challenges and modernise industry. The Horizon Europe proposal lays down the conditions and principles for establishing European Partnerships.

³⁷ EIT Knowledge and Innovation Communities (KICs) are also institutionalised partnerships. EIT KICs address skills shortages. Key partners in EIT KICs are higher education institutions, research organisations, companies and other stakeholders.

³⁸ https://new-european-bauhaus.europa.eu/index_en

CCS on a cross-sectorial approach and build “bridges between the world of science and technology, art and culture” to work across policy domains.

It should be highlighted that each CCS network has its separate entry in the institutional setup. Design, architecture and “high end industries” will find the ears of DG GROW, audio-visual with DG CONNECT, music and NGOs with DGEAC. DG INTPA / NEAR, DG REGIO, DG RTD will interact little with CCS networks in their industrial dimension.

The picture below shows the most relevant interactions between the various CCS policy networks and EC services.

Figure 2. Flow diagram of main interactions between CCS policy networks and the European Commission DGs

Source: KEA

2.3 The effect of CCS representation on EU policies: a lack of coherence in policy actions

The inadequate CCS representation is reflected in the content of EU policy documents which document a diverse understanding of CCS and its constituents.

- On 10 March 2020, the European Commission laid the foundations for an industrial strategy that would support the twin transition to a green and digital economy, make EU industry more competitive globally, and enhance Europe’s open strategic autonomy. The EC identified 14 industrial ecosystems – among them “the cultural and creative industries”³⁹.
- On 4 April 2022 the Council adopted a Resolution on “the building of a European strategy for a cultural and creative industry ecosystem”⁴⁰. The document highlights the role played by CCSI in the green transition, social cohesion, regional development, and local regeneration. It underlines the importance of stimulating a competitive industry and addresses the power of global digital players, “acting as gatekeepers in the digital market” calling on the development of a strategy that includes:
 - Better access to funding.
 - Spurring skills development.
 - Maintain the strategy autonomy of CCIS in the digital era.

It is unclear who will be responsible for implementing this Resolution and how the CCS will be consulted to ensure that as an ecosystem it can co-create a “transition pathway” currently being developed for other industries.⁴¹

- On the other hand, a few months later, on 29 November 2022, the Council of Culture Ministers of the EU adopted a Resolution on the EU Work Plan for Culture 2023-2026.⁴² It sets out priorities to address the main challenges facing the cultural and creative sectors today and corresponding actions to address them. The resolution identifies four priorities, which are quite different from the above Resolution. It reads as follows:
 - artists and cultural professionals: empowering the cultural and creative sectors;

³⁹ European Commission (2021). Updating the 2020 New Industrial Strategy: Building a stronger Single Market for Europe’s recovery. Communication from the Commission to the European Parliament, the Council, the European Economic and Social Committee and the Committee of the Regions. Retrieved from https://commission.europa.eu/system/files/2021-05/communication-industrial-strategy-update-2020_en.pdf

⁴⁰ European Council. (2022). Council Conclusions on Building a European Strategy for the Cultural and Creative Industries Ecosystem (<https://data.consilium.europa.eu/doc/document/ST-7809-2022-INIT/xx/pdf>)

⁴¹ https://single-market-economy.ec.europa.eu/industry/transition-pathways_en - Tourism will benefit from such programme.

⁴² Ibid. European Council (2022) Council Resolution on the EU Work Plan for Culture 2023-2026 (2022/C 466/01). Retrieved from <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX%3A32022G1207%2801%29>

- culture for the people: enhancing cultural participation and the role of culture in society;
- culture for the planet: unleashing the power of culture; and
- culture for co-creative partnerships: strengthening the cultural dimension of the EU external relations.

The current Work Plan's priorities are broadly in line with the Commission's [Report on the Work Plan for Culture 2019-2022](#). Among the proposed future priorities are also listed: *"the recovery and resilience of the cultural sectors, the effects of climate change, culture's role for societal transformation and well-being or the combatting of illicit trade in cultural goods"*.

From reading these recent policy papers, the EU is advancing on the basis of different sets of policy priorities for CCS. It shows the need to develop a shared vision across policy departments and institutions.

To conclude the CCS is identified by EU policymakers as a major economic sector with significant social and cultural value. A differentiation between CCS and CCSI (or CCIE) leads to different policy treatments, with objectives addressing part of the CCS and excluding others as if there were not part of the same ecosystem or production network.

3. Cultural and creative sector representation and policy gaps

This somewhat limited understanding of the CCS, with a siloed approach exacerbated by substantial data gaps, is under-estimating the actual (economic, cultural, and social) values of the sector, thus questioning the focus and objectives of policymaking and as a result its impact.

The CICERONE project researched the ‘actually existing’ CCS. We began not from the Eurostat definitions of the industries and activities, but with a selection of the industries and activities that constitute the CCS: mapping their organisational forms, and the flows of goods, services, and people. This approach goes beyond inputs and outputs and explores how flows are directed and governed. Viewing the CCS as ‘an industrial sector’ does not involve a value judgement but simply expands our visibility and the focus of the lens of analysis to reflect the complexity of reality.

If we do not grasp the value of CCS and its way of operation, are we making the most of it? Is the support (whether financial or regulatory) missing critical bottlenecks? Would a better information flow help the industry to be more active in shaping the research agenda, including the EIT KIC initiative? A CCS representation that helps make sense of the digital revolution’s impact and is in a position to address current global challenges should be considered. This would contribute to considering the new dynamics and better exploiting the cross-over potential.

The CICERONE model of the CCS with its flows, spatial and organisational perspectives was compared to that of the extant data sources for the CCS that are available via Eurostat based on national census data. The research highlighted that the Eurostat data was even more partial than suspected and from the perspective of a GPN network identified the strategic value of some gaps above others. Data gaps naturally translate into policy gaps.

In a series of workshops with CCS representatives held in Autumn 2022,⁴³ a number of policy gaps were identified. The policy forum held on 23 March in Brussels was the opportunity to discuss the policy gaps identified below.

The groups identified shared characteristic of CCS:

- Intrinsic motivation to work in the CCS whether at management and staff level considering the value and meanings of working for the arts and culture.
- The need to recognize the distinction between (economic) value capture vs (economic) value creation when assessing the importance of CCS.

⁴³ List of invitees and attendees are found in the Annexes.

- The capacity of CCS to foster social transformation, pluralism, freedom of expression, democracy, gender, cultural diversity, increase the quality of life more generally.
- The importance of public support to encourage the setting up of an environment conducive to the emergence of new talents, new creations, and production as well as educating audiences (notably through art education).

The outcomes of the workshops showed that the current understanding of CCS prevents:

- The CCS to articulate policy needs beyond their sectoral agenda, thus affecting the capacity to influence more expansive policy areas linked to innovation, research, social resilience, territorial regeneration, skills requirements, intercultural dialogue, health, or green transition issues along the whole production network.
- Policymakers at all governance levels (local, national, European) to consider more effective policy initiatives that address CCS's needs.
- CCS policy networks to be engaged on all policy fronts notably on trans-sectoral policy issues linked to addressing global challenges.

The workshops showed that strategic reflections across the various phases of the production network, require policy intervention based on four pillars:

- Capacity-building and support for the transition to sustainability and digitalisation.
- Addressing regulatory issues, working conditions, improving market access, cultural participation, and mobility.
- Improving access to financing.
- Strengthening the CCS resilience and cultural diversity.

Concerning these pillars, the following policy gaps were identified by the participants:

- Concerning capacity building and support for sustainability and digitalisation
 - Improve CCS representation in Horizon Europe research agenda (beyond cultural heritage) and adapt research agenda to CCS priorities (notably on artificial intelligence).
 - Talent skills for a new digital ecosystem (skills shortage and talent retention are issues).
 - Improve skills at the administrative level to promote understanding of the cultural and creative economy.
 - Support policies aimed at building audiences for European works (education).
 - Functional capacity of Ministries of Culture to integrate the production network dimension.
 - Resources national statistical offices to capture the diverse values of CCS (economic and societal).
 - Labour shortages in specific subsectors notably in creation and production phases (technical and creative skills).
 - The need to create scale to reinforce bargaining position notably with digital gatekeepers.
 - Uncoordinated actions with policy initiatives taken at local and regional policies in the field of training and incubation (city / creative hubs).

- Development of European platforms or to prevent the risk of losing European intellectual property to other countries (USA and China).
 - Improve mapping of employment in the CCS and the video game market in particular.
 - Digitisation of film, publishing, fashion and music heritage for future inspiration and exploitation (archiving phase).
 - Considerable data gaps that affect the actual economic value of the sector and which do not allow to capture values in all its dimensions (notably creation, social and ethical values). More qualitative data are required for a better understanding of the sector. The collection of quantitative data is to be standardized and NACE codes amended⁴⁴.
 - Develop European data on cultural participation and new cultural practices as well as gender employment in CCS.
 - Insufficient account of spillover impact of CCS, notably on innovation.
 - Policies reinforce divisions between the non-commercial cultural sector and cultural industries rather than promoting joint collective actions.
 - Consider CCS in international partnerships also in its economic dimension as a way to support economic growth, employment but also regional cohesion (e.g., West Balkans).
- Concerning regulatory issues:
- Help monetise value creation vs value capture for European creators and producers to benefit from global distribution revenues.
 - Monitor obligations to promote European works on digital platforms.
 - Implement competition policies towards digital streamers / gatekeepers in a strong market position to prevent abuse.
 - Data gaps and availability of data from gatekeepers; how to address this?
 - Improve labour conditions of cultural workers to address social precarity.
- Concerning access to financing
- Focus on support should be wider than the film sector and the production phases (EU Guarantee Facility).
 - Financial institutions showing interests in the CCS should be encouraged to share good practices in financing CCS (as an outcome of the capacity building delivered to financial intermediaries as part of the deployment of the EU Guarantee Facility for CCS⁴⁵).
 - Reinforce capacity building of CCS to access financial institutions and for financial institutions to understand CCS.
 - Financing at distribution and exchange phases should be given priority to encourage market access and digital distribution of European creation (ex: South Korea).
 - Trends in rights acquisition by venture capital funds and financial institutions should be considered as far as they impact the value of cultural productions.

⁴⁴ The DISCE project is a EU funded project that aims to support the development of CCIs patterns through improved statistical indicators; it addresses the existing data gaps. <https://disce.eu/>

⁴⁵ https://ec.europa.eu/commission/presscorner/detail/it/MEMO_16_2346

- Strengthening CCS resilience and cultural diversity:
 - Support a new narrative to show the broader contribution of CCS – etc. / Green and digital transition and mobilise creative skills to address the challenges.
 - Promote cross-sectorial and trans-disciplinary collaboration.
 - Assess the role of public authorities (local, national, European) in supporting CCS to address challenges most effectively and in partnership.
 - Harmonise the status of cultural entrepreneurs, and artists and support mobility of artists and cultural workers. There is a clear lack of European data on working conditions in CCS.
 - Get CCS to contribute to debate on the impact of artificial intelligence and innovation with societal impact.

The discussion with CCS networks leads to the following critical remarks:

- Policy objectives are too focused on addressing national cultural policy issues with a lack of consideration for CCS European and international challenges. Vision and foresight are necessary considering the market and technological developments.
- National cultural ministries are not always best positioned or in the capacity to address broader regulatory issues that impact CCS as global production network.
- Policy-making at EU level is of extreme importance considering the regulatory power of the EU in areas that impact CCS (notably copyright, trade, competition issues). Member States should remain in control of their cultural priorities but with guidance on international trends and issues.
- CCS stakeholders have to make sense of the various levels of policy interactions between the different services at the EU level. This consumes considerable human and technical resources, which makes CCS representation more costly and less efficient.
- Financial resources are a central issue to enable proper CCS representation at the policy or research level. The EU has been instrumental in enabling CCS representation, notably in the not-for-profit sector. It remains that important policy or research initiatives do not find echo at the industrial level.
- CCS stakeholders understand the need to speak with one voice and increasingly on an ad-hoc basis as coalitions of CCS networks are emerging to state a common position. They see the need to develop a joint narrative on the role played by culture in societal transformation and European integration. This will support the mainstreaming of culture in other policy areas.
- It would be interesting to evaluate the impact of the AV Observatory on policy decisions as well as the impact of CCS on the Horizon Europe programme.
- It is essential to include the regional and local dimension in policy making.
- More coherence is required in EU policy-making to avoid too many and divergent policy priorities whether CCS issues are discussed at cultural or industrial policy levels. The development of an EU Cultural Policy Framework to provide more coherence should be considered.

The policy forum held on 23 March in Brussels was the opportunity to discuss and endorse the above policy gaps.

4. Recommendations

The environment in which CCS evolve has dramatically changed. GPN well describes this environment. It shows that CCS need to revisit the way they influence policy-making. The organisations' needs can be characterized by the following examples:

- Centres of production are localised, and distribution is internationalised. Policies are excessively territorial focusing on creation and production whilst value is captured in strongly capitalised global digital streaming services and global brands. Promoting cultural diversity implies more efforts at distribution and exchange levels to fight the low market share of European creation in foreign markets. How to make the local have a global impact across sectors?
- The GPN's strengths lie in capturing the dynamic between actors in the production network locally and internationally. Information on the dynamics and co-dependency between leading companies, strategic partners, specialised suppliers, and distributors is essential. The various players have a strategic role in the value chain that makes them indispensable, but they need targeted policy support to consider their specific contributions. Policymakers need to understand the dynamics better and strengthen relationships with strategic partners in CCS similar to how they developed strategic partnerships in other sectors (technology, energy, manufacturing).
- A better appreciation of cultural and social impact calls for the mobilisation of the policy networks to reflect on their capacity to develop a new understanding and influence policy-making beyond a sectoral and siloed approach.
- Working methods and practices are increasingly trans-sectorial with more value given by CCS entrepreneurs to the social impact and artistic value of production. GPN also highlights organizational changes (often linked to financial, technology, or behavioral transformation) and the impact of such changes on the network. These organisational changes are often not apprehended at policy level as CCS are siloed in sectors and production phases. Are we capturing this critical characteristic of CCS? Are they being expressed by CCS representatives?
- A CCS GPN lens helps us see the vast array of labour situations (self-employed, employed, part-time/full-time, interns, volunteers, etc.) which are often not captured thus undermining the true social impact of CCS or the consequences of policies on labour situation. Policymakers do not sufficiently apprehend this characteristic of CCS. Digital transactions and processes require new skills which are necessary to acquire for creation and production to create values. Are we addressing these gaps in skill and training?
- Networks overlap with different CCS or other industries, notably in digital and manufacturing (thus showing cross-over potential). The GPN approach helps to apprehend the spillover impact of cultural investment; and the importance of supporting and sustaining CCS production ecosystems. CCS representation needs to reflect the spill-over potential of CCS. Policy-makers

should encourage the development of cross-sectorial representation and initiatives with large-scale funding support.

- The approach also reveals the hybrid relationships between for-profit and not-for-profit activities (thus showing an essential characteristic of CCS activities) not accounted for when valuing the impact of CCS. It highlights how CCS are actors of transformation able to achieve broader policy objectives such as sustainability, competitiveness, cultural diversity, and social inclusion goals. Policy initiatives should create paths for increased collaboration between the industrial and non-industrial networks.
- Cities and regions have become essential drivers and contributors of production networks as part of urban regeneration and territorial attractiveness. How to interconnect local creative hubs with global production networks?

CCS representation has to reflect this new reality and enable the expression of a new set of values in a transdisciplinary spirit to imagine a future that does not discount the cultural and artistic elements. In this respect, CCS policy networks should consider setting up a coordination vehicle responsible for considering trans and cross-sectorial issues. To this effect, it is proposed to support building “Creative Europe” as a network uniting the various CCS policy networks to enable better engagement with cross-sectorial policy initiatives on skills, and digital and green transformation, enabling the scaling up of CCS ecosystems.

Creative Europe as an institutional network or “a CCS Alliance” would be responsible for supporting the deployment of the CCS observatory that would complement the work done by the AV Observatory and EUROSTAT.

In addition, considering the importance taken by CCS, policy-making should adapt as well:

- More coherence is required in policy actions and the development of a EU Cultural Policy Frameworks should be considered as a matter of priority to ensure consistency between various initiatives and help CCS networks to target their contributions across a manageable number of policy units.
- Support should be provided to set up the proposed CCS Observatory to improve intelligence on CCS and understanding of impact of policy measures. The Observatory is a necessary tool to improve CCS governance and to give shape to the new lenses provided by the GPN approach (“a whole network” perspective). The Observatory would be an essential tool to promote cross-sectorial engagement of CCS policy networks as they would have an interest in providing data and make use of such data to provide evidence. Work on the observatory should feed in ongoing work to revise the statistical framework. As proposed by Eurostat representatives at the Cicerone Policy Forum on 23 March 2023, concrete steps should be taken to operationalize the CCS Observatory beyond the pilot phase.
- Policy-makers should embrace a cross-sectorial vision of CCS and consider the perspectives given by the GPN approach when organizing consultation with CCS to design policies. The setting up of a transnational CCS Alliance to cover the entire CCS production network and call for action on key

policy priorities should be encouraged in line with successful national initiatives. The CCS Alliance could be mandated to reflect on the following trans-sectorial policy topics for instance:

- Contribution to innovation and societal transformation with a view to address the Green Deal and Sustainable Development Goals.
 - Improve skills, training and working conditions.
 - Develop access to finance and consider the impact of financial models and rights acquisition which impact/threaten economic value of cultural productions.
 - Apprehend and influence technology development to the benefit of CCS and society.
- The CCS Alliance would also identify research topics for funding under Horizon Europe. In this respect, Horizon Europe could support developing a CCS European Partnership. CCS, to the exclusion of cultural heritage, is notoriously absent from EU research policy. This should be addressed as a priority considering the technology (AI) and market challenges.

The CCS Alliance would give concrete shape to the concept of cultural and creative sector and enable the latter to be identified as other industries that are more effective in representing their interests at EU level such as tourism (see Europe Tourism Manifesto – Priorities gathering 70 associations involved in tourism) for instance.

Table 4. Summary of main policy recommendations

Objectives	Means
Increase level of CCS engagement and support collective action / Build capacity	Support cross-sectoral collaborations and transversal actions through the setting up of a CCS Alliance and encourage a CCS-powered European Partnership under Horizon Europe.
Improve data on CCS/ Build capacity	Develop the CCS Observatory and integrate the GPN approach to improve knowledge of the CCS.
Coherence in EU cultural policy	Work on a EU CCS Policy Framework

Appendix A. CCS policy networks at EU level

Table 5. List of 112 CCS policy networks at EU level

Acronym	Name of the organization
ACE	Architects Council of Europe
ACE-Film	Association of European Film Archives and Cinematheques
ACT	European Association of Commercial Televisions
AEAA	European Association of Artist Managers
AEC	Association Européenne des Conservatoires, Académies de Musique et Musikhochschulen
AEPO/ARTIS	Association of European Performers Organisations
AER	Association of European Radios
b.creative	Global network for cultural and creative entrepreneurs
BEDA	The Bureau of European Design Associations
CAE	Culture Action Europe
CBNET	Creative Business Network
CELA	Connecting emerging literary artists
Circostrada Network	European Network for contemporary circus and outdoor arts.
Classical Futures Europe	EU funded platform supporting emerging artists in the field of classical music
CN	Culture Next
CPDN	Cultural Policy Designers Network
Creative Ring	Network for creative people
Creativity Works!	Coalition of organisations, federations and associations representing Europe's cultural and creative sectors
DIGITAL EUROPE	Association representing European digitally transforming industries
DME	Digital Music Europe
DOT Europe	Association representing Digital Online Tech
EAA	European Association of Archaeologists
EAN	European-art.net
EBN	European Business Network
EBU	European Broadcaster's Union

ECA-EC	European Choral Association
ECBN	European Creative Business Network
ECBN	European Network for Creative Industries
ECCIA	European Cultural and Creative Industries Alliance
ECCO	European Confederation of Conservator-Restorers' Organisations
ECF	European Cultural Foundation
ECHN	European Creative Hubs Network
ECHO	European Concert Hall Organization
ECIA	European Council of Interior Architect
ECSA	European Composer and Songwriter Alliance
ECTN	European Cultural Tourism Network
EDN	European Dancehouse Network
EEPAP	East European Performing Arts Platform
EFA	European Fashion Alliance
EFA-AEF	European Festivals Association
EFAD	European Film Agency Directors
EFC	European Fashion Council
EFHA	European Fashion Heritage Association
EFP	European Film Promotion
EGTA	European Group of Television Advertising
EIBF	European and International Bookseller Federation
EIF	European Illustrators Forum
EJN	European Jazz Network
ELIA	European League of Institutes for the Arts
ELMA	European Live Music Association
EMC	European Music Council
EMEE	European Music Exporters Exchange
EMMA	The European Music Managers Alliance
ENCATC	European Network on Cultural management and Policy Education
ENCC	European Network of Cultural Centres (ENCC)
ERIH	European Route of Industrial Heritage

ERRIN	European Regions Research and Innovation Network
ESACH	European Students' Association for Cultural Heritage
ETC	European Theatre Convention
EU Culture Alliance	European networks advocating for including culture and the arts in the strategic goals of the European Union.
EUNIC	EU National Institutes of Culture
EURATEX	European Apparel and Textile Confederation
EUROCITIES	Network of large cities in Europe
Europa Distribution	Network of independent European film distributors
Europa Nostra	The European Voice of Civil Society committed to Cultural Heritage
European Film Academy	Network of European Film Professionals
European VOD Coalition	Association representing VOD and digital-entertainment companies
Europeana	A web portal created by the European Union containing digitised cultural heritage collections of more than 3,000 institutions across Europe.
EUROVOD	Network of European Independent VOD Platforms
Eurozine	European Network of Cultural Journals
EUVOD	European Video on Demand Coalition
EVA	European Visual Artists
EWC	European Writers Council
F.E.A.G.A.	Federation of European Art Galleries Associations
FERA	Federation of European Film Directors
FEST	Federation for European Storytelling
FIA	International Federation of Artists
FRH	Future for Religious Heritage
GESAC	European Union of Societies of Authors and Composers
HERIT	European Historic Houses Association
IAA	International Association of Art Europe
ICOM	International Council of Museums
ICOMOS Europe	International Council on Monuments and Sites
IETM	International network for contemporary performing arts
IFACCA	International Federation of Arts Councils and Culture Agencies
IFLA EUROPA	International Federation of Landscape Architects

IFM - FIM	International Federation of Musicians
IFPI	International Federation of the Phonographic Industry
IMMF	International Music Managers Forum
IMPALA	Independent Music Companies Association
IMPF	Independent Music Publishers International Forum
Interpret Europe	European Association for Heritage Interpretation
IOBA	The Independent Online Booksellers Association
ISFE	Interactive Software Federation of Europe
LIVE DMA	European network of live music associations
Liveurope	Network of international concert venues in Europe
MADinEurope	Network of European fine and traditional crafts and Cultural Heritage restoration professions
Michael Culture Association	European trans domain network for Cultural Heritage
Motion Picture Association	Association representing the global film, television, and streaming industry
NEMO	Network of European Museum Organisations
On the Move	Network for European cultural mobility.
Opera Europa	Service organisation for professional opera companies and opera festivals in Europe
Pearle	Pearle* Live Performance Europe
Pen International	International Organization for Writers
REMA	European Early Music Network
SAA	Society of Audiovisual Authors
TEH	Trans Europe Halles
UNI Europa	The European Services Workers Union
UNIC	International Union of Cinemas
WCC Europe	World Crafts Council Europe
We are Europe	A Creative Europe project to formulate and advance a new vision of Europe
YOUROPE	The European Festival Association

Appendix B. Acronyms of CCS policy networks

Table 6. Acronyms of CCS policy networks

Acronym	Name of the Policy Network
ACE	Architecture Council of Europe
ACT	Association of Commercial Television
AEPO-ARTIS	Association of European Performers' Organisations
b.creative	Network of Cultural and Creative Entrepreneurs
BEDA	Bureau of European Design Associations
CAE	Culture Action Europe
Creative Business Network	Network of creative startups and investors
CEIPI	Center for International Intellectual Property Studies
CELA	Connecting emerging literary artists
CLICKNL	The Dutch Creative Industries knowledge and innovation network
CoECI	Centre of Expertise for Creative Innovation
Creative Flip	Preparatory Action to strengthen the resilience of CCSIs
Creative Estonia	CCI Cluster and development center in Estonia
Creative UK	UK Culture and Creative sector Network
Creative Works!	Coalition of organisations, federations and associations representing Europe's cultural and creative sectors
DDF	Dutch Design Foundation
DIGITAL EUROPE	Association representing European digitally transforming industries
DOT Europe	Association representing Digital Online Tech
EBU	European Broadcasting Union
ECBN	European Creative Business Network
ECCIA	European Cultural and Creative Industries Alliance

ECF	European Cultural Foundation
ECSA	European Composer and Songwriter Alliance
EFA	European Fashion Alliance
EFAD	European Film Agency Directors
EFC	European Fashion Council
EFHA	European Fashion Heritage Association
EIT	European Institute of Technology
ENCC	European Network of Cultural Centres
ERRIN	European Regions Research and Innovation Network
EUNIC	European National Institute for Culture
EURATEX	European Apparel and Textile Confederation
EUROCITIES	Network of large cities in Europe
EUROPA NOSTRA	The European Voice of Civil Society committed to Cultural Heritage
European VOD Coalition	Association representing VOD and digital-entertainment companies
EUROVOD	Network of European Independent VOD Platforms
EVA	European Visual Artists
FCI	Federatie Creatieve Industrie
FEP	Federation of European Publishers
FERA	Federation of European Screen Directors
FIA	International Federation of Actors
FIM	International Federation of Musicians
GESAC	European Union of Societies of Authors and Composers
IETM	International network for contemporary performing arts
IFPI	International Federation of the Phonographic Industries
IMPALA	Independent Music Companies Association
ISFE	Interactive Software Federation of Europe

KAT	Kreativwirtschaft Austria
KIC	Knowledge Innovation Community
MME	Music Moves Europe
Motion Picture Association	Association representing the global film, television, and streaming industry
NEMO	Network of European Museums Organizations
SAA	Society of Audiovisual Authors
TEH	Trans Europe Halles